

OPTIMAL DESIGN of HYBRID LAMINATED COMPOSITE PLATES
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ABSTRACT

In this paper, optimization procedure are presented with considering the static and dynamic characteristic constraints for laminated composite plates and hybrid laminated composite plates subject to concentrated load on center of plate.

Design variables adopted ply angle or ply thickness. Considered constraints are deflection, natural frequency and specific damping capacity.

Using a recursive linear programming method, nonlinear optimization problems are solved, and by introducing the design scaling factor, the number of iteration is reduced significantly. Relating interactive optimization procedures with the finite element method analysis, various hybrid composite plates of arbitrary boundary condition can be designed optimally.

In the optimization procedure, verification of analysis and design of the laminated composite plates are compare to the previous paper. Various design results are presented on laminated composite plates and hybrid laminated composite plates.

KEYWORDS: Hybrid; Optimization; damping; Design methodology;
Recursive linear programming.

1. INTRODUCTION

Because of the outstanding strength, stiffness and low specific gravity of fibers, low maintenance costs, and the flexibility in tailoring of composite

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materials, the use of composite materials increase in engineering fields, and optimal design of composite structures is significant aimed to reduced structural weight.

The optimal design of laminated composite plates has been a subject of research for many years. Several papers have been published on the optimum design of laminated plates under in-plane loading,^[1] subject to shear buckling^[2] and flexure^{[3][4]}. Watkins and Morris^[5] have presented a multilevel optimization scheme for the design of laminated plate elements subjected to buckling and stress constraints. Recently Kam and Chang^[6] have presented a multilevel optimization procedure for the minimum weight design of the plates subjected to frequency, specific damping capacity(S.D.C.) and displacement constraints.

The purpose of this paper is to present the minimum weight design used to a recursive linear programming method for the composite plates and hybrid composite plates to include aluminum layer subject to concentrate load. The optimal design of the plate subject to frequency, specific damping capacity (S.D.C.) and displacement constraints is presented. Ply thicknesses or orientations are designed to minimize the volume of the plates. The finite element analysis of a plate is achieved by utilizing the element proposed by Reddy^[7], and the damping model developed by Lins and coworkers^[8] is adopted in the optimal design of plates. Several examples are given to demonstrate the applications of the proposed method.

2. ANALYSIS OF HYBRID LAMINATED COMPOSITE PLATE

2.1 Finite Element Analysis In the present finite element model of a composite plate and a hybrid laminated composite plate, the C^0 (penalty) finite element developed by Reddy^[7] is adopted for the structural and free vibration analysis. The element contains five degree-of-freedom, i.e. three displacements (u , v , w) and two slopes(ψ_x , ψ_y), per node. The terms of the element stiffness matrix, K^e , are given in Ref.[6,7].

The equations of motion of the plate are expressed in matrix form as

$$\left[M^e \right] \left\{ \dot{U}^e \right\} + \left[K^e \right] \left\{ U^e \right\} = \left\{ F^e \right\} \quad (1)$$

Where M is the global mass matrix, K is the global stiffness matrix, U and \ddot{U} are vectors of nodal displacements and accelerations, respectively, and F is vector of nodal forces. For static analysis, eqn(1) reduces to

$$[K] \{U\} = \{F\} \quad (2)$$

For free vibration case, eqn (1) becomes an eigenvalue problem,

$$([K] - \omega^2 [M]) \{v\} = 0 \quad (3)$$

Where ω is the frequency of the natural vibration, Hz/rad, and v the mode shape vector.

2.2 Analysis of Specific Damping Capacity(S.D.C.)

The model for structure damping of a composite plate is based on the work of Lin^[8] as same as Kam^[6]. The specific damping, Ψ , associate with the flexural response of the plate, may be defined as

$$\Psi = \frac{\Delta U_m}{U_m} \quad (4)$$

Where ΔU_m is the energy dissipated during a stress cycle and U_m is the total strain energy. In the finite element analysis, the total strain energy is expressed as^[6]

$$U_m = \frac{1}{2} \{v\}^T [K] \{v\} \quad (5)$$

and the dissipated energy is expressed as

$$\Delta U_m = \frac{1}{2} \{v\}^T [K_d] \{v\} \quad (6)$$

Where K_d is the assembled global damped stiffness matrix. The element damped matrix is expressed as

$$[K_d^e] = \sum_{k=1}^n \int_{A^e} \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} (B_{ij})_k^T [T^{-1}] (\Psi_{ij})_k (Q_{ij})_k [T^{-T}] (B_{ij})_k dz dA^e \quad (7)$$

Where $(B_{ij})_k$ is a matrix of the derivatives of the element shape functions, T is a coordinate transformation matrix, $(Q_{ij})_k$ is a matrix of material stiffnesses, and $(\Psi_{ij})_k$ is a matrix of S.D.C.. $(\Psi_{ij})_k$ is expressed as^{[6],[8]}

$$\Psi_{ij} = \begin{bmatrix} \Psi_{11} & & & & 0 \\ & \Psi_{22} & & & \\ & & \Psi_{23} & & \\ & & & \Psi_{13} & \\ 0 & & & & \Psi_{12} \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

Where Ψ_{11} , Ψ_{22} are the S.D.C. of beam specimens with ply angle 0° and 90° , respectively, which are tested in flexure and Ψ_{12} , Ψ_{23} , Ψ_{13} are the S.D.C. of 0° and 90° specimens in longitudinal shear.

3. OPTIMIZATION PROCEDURE

3.1 Problem Formulation

The problem is to find the fiber thicknesses of layers which give the minimum weight of a hybrid laminated composite plate subject to behavioral constraints as well as side constraints. It is expressed as

$$\text{Minimize } \Phi_0(t_i) = A \cdot \sum_{k=1}^n \rho_k \cdot t_k \quad (9)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Subject to } \quad g_1(t_i) &= U_k - U_k \leq 0, \quad (k = 1, \dots, m) \\ g_2(t_i) &= -\omega_1^2 + \overline{\omega_1^2} \leq 0 \\ g_3(t_i) &= -\Psi + \overline{\Psi} \leq 0 \\ t_i^l &\leq t_i \leq t_i^u \\ t_i &\geq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Where n is the number of plies per a hybrid laminated composite plate, m is the number of nodal displacement vectors, Φ_0 is objective function, g_i constraint equations, A is area of a plate, ρ_k is density of the k -th layer, and t_i^l and t_i^u are a lower bound and an upper bound of the i -th layer thickness. Superscript(-) means to the previous value of design step.

Hence, to find the fiber directions of layers, a multi-objective optimization problem is adopted. The problem can be written as

$$\text{Minimize } \Phi_0(\theta_i) = \sum_{j=1}^m q_j U_{nj} - q_{m+1} \cdot f_n - q_{m+2} \cdot \Psi_n \quad (11)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Subject to } \quad U_{nj} &\leq 1 \quad (j = 1, \dots, m) \\ -f_n &\leq -1 \\ -\Psi_n &\leq -1 \\ \theta_i^l &\leq \theta_i \leq \theta_i^u \\ \theta_i &\geq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

Where U_n , f_n , and Ψ_n are $U_n = U_j / \overline{U}_j$, $f_n = f_1 / \overline{f}_1$, $\Psi_n = \Psi / \overline{\Psi}$. f is the natural frequency, Hz. q_i is defined as $\sum q_i = 1$ by Watkins and Morris^[5].

3.2 Linearization of the Functions

To use of the recursive linear programming method, the linearized form of eqn(9)

and (10), using a first-order Taylor expansion, is thus

$$\text{Minimize } \Phi_0(t_i) = A \cdot \sum_{k=1}^n \rho_k \cdot t_k \quad (13)$$

$$\text{Subject to } g_1(t_i) = U_k - \bar{U}_k + \Delta t_i \frac{\partial U_k}{\partial t_i} \quad (k = 1, \dots, m)$$

$$g_2(t_i) = -\omega_1^2 + \bar{\omega}_1^2 + \Delta t_i \frac{\partial \omega_1^2}{\partial t_i} \quad (14)$$

$$g_3(t_i) = -\Psi + \bar{\Psi} + \Delta t_i \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial t_i}$$

$$t_i^l \leq t_i \leq t_i^u$$

$$t_i \geq 0$$

Where, Δt_i is the deviation of a initial values of design step and a values at the point of linearization, $t-t_0$. Eqn (11) and (12) are written by the same method as the following

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Minimize } \Phi_0(\theta_i) &= \sum_{j=1}^m q_j (U_{nj} + \Delta \theta_i \frac{\partial U_{nj}}{\partial \theta_i}) \\ &\quad - q_{m+1} (f_n + \Delta \theta_i \frac{\partial f_n}{\partial \theta_i}) - q_{m+2} (\Psi_n^2 + \Delta \theta_i \frac{\partial \Psi_n^2}{\partial \theta_i}) \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Subject to } U_{nj} + \Delta \theta_i \frac{\partial U_{nj}}{\partial \theta_i} &\leq 1 \quad (j = 1, \dots, m) \\ - f_n - \Delta \theta_i \frac{\partial f_n}{\partial \theta_i} &\leq -1 \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

$$- \Psi_n - \Delta \theta_i \frac{\partial \Psi_n}{\partial \theta_i} \leq -1$$

$$\theta_i^l \leq \theta_i \leq \theta_i^u$$

$$\theta_i \geq 0$$

Where, $\Delta \theta_i$ is the deviation of a initial values of design step and a values at the point of linearization, $\theta-\theta_0$. The derivatives of U , ω_1^2 , and Ψ with respect to design variables, θ and t , are required for performing the above optimization problems. Expressions for the derivatives are well known and can be found in Ref.[5,6]. As a method to define the bound of design variables, t_i and θ_j are proposed by Watkins and Morris^[5] as following

$$\begin{aligned} t_i^u &= \{ 1 + 0.5 (0.95)^{k-1} \} t_{k-1} \\ t_i^l &= \{ 1 + 0.5 (0.95)^{k-1} \} t_{k-1} \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

$$\theta_j^u = \theta_{k-1} + 15 (0.9)$$

$$\theta_j^l = \theta_{k-1} - 15 (0.9)^{k-1}$$

3.3 Design Scaling Factor

The objective function and constraint equations are non-linear equation, the optimization procedure to use a recursive linear programming method take a late convergence speed and lower accuracy then a mathematical programming method. Therefore, we need to select a design scaling factor. This paper is proposed following method. The matrix form of eqn (13), (14) is

$$\text{Minimize} \quad f(x) = C_i^T X_i \quad (i=1, \dots, N_d) \quad (18)$$

$$\text{Subject to} \quad [E_{ij}]^T X_i \leq H_j \quad (j=1, \dots, N_c) \quad (19)$$

Where, C_i is the coefficient vector of objective function, E_{ij} is the coefficient vector of constraint equations, N_d is the number of design variables, N_c is the number of constraint equations, X_i is the deviation of initial value of design step and a value at the point of linearization, $X-X_0$. Hence X_i is the solution of linear eqns (13), (14), and not the solution of non-linear eqns (9), (10). Let

$$Y_i = \left\{ \gamma X_i^n \right\} \quad (20)$$

Where, Y_i is the solution of eqns(9), (10). γ is the design scaling factor to related X_i and Y_i . In the relation of eqns(17) and (18), we obtain the function of γ .

$$f(\gamma) = \gamma C_t^T X_t^n \quad (21)$$

As the function of γ , eqn (10) is expressed to

$$R(\gamma) = \{1 - U_n(\gamma)\} + |\omega_n^2(\gamma) - 1| + |\Psi_n(\gamma) - 1| \quad (22)$$

Where, $U_n(\gamma) = \bar{U}/U$, $\omega_n(\gamma) = \bar{\omega}/\omega$, $\Psi_n(\gamma) = \bar{\Psi}_n/\Psi_n$. By the least square method, eqn (20) is

$$\text{Minimize} \quad \varepsilon(\gamma) = s\{1 - U_n(\gamma)\}^2 + \{f_n(\gamma) - 1\}^2 + \{\Psi_n(\gamma) - 1\}^2 \quad (23)$$

Where, s is the sign function, i.e. when $U_n(\gamma) \geq 1$, s is the minus sign. In eqn(21), $U_n(\gamma)$, $f_n(\gamma)$ and $\Psi_n(\gamma)$ to be linearized, is

$$\begin{aligned} U_n(\gamma) &\cong U_n^0(\gamma) + \nabla U_n^T \cdot X_i^n \cdot \gamma \\ f_n(\gamma) &\cong f_n^0(\gamma) + (\nabla f_n)^T \cdot X_i^n \cdot \gamma \\ \Psi_n(\gamma) &\cong \Psi_n^0(\gamma) + \nabla \Psi_n^T \cdot X_i^n \cdot \gamma \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

In eqns(21) and (22), the design scaling factor, γ , which the first order

derivation of $\varepsilon(\gamma)$ is zero, is

$$\gamma = \frac{[s(1-U_n^0)\nabla U_n^T \cdot X_i^n - (f_n^0-1)(\nabla f_n)^T \cdot X_i^n - (\Psi_n^0-1)\nabla \Psi_n^T \cdot X_i^n]}{[s[\nabla U_n^T \cdot X_i^n]^2 + \{(\nabla f_n)^T \cdot X_i^n\}^2 + \{\nabla \Psi_n^T \cdot X_i^n\}^2]} \quad (25)$$

Where, ∇ is gradient. When design point is far, γX_i^n is very large value enough to be out of design region. When design point is neighboring γX_i^n is very small value. Therefore, when γX_i^n is very large, to prevent to invisible design region, we take the following equation to be considered eqn(16)

$$t_i^k = t_i^{k-1} + t_i^B \frac{\gamma X_i^n}{\max(|\gamma X_i^n|)} \quad (26)$$

$$t_i^k \geq 0$$

Where, k is a number of design step. t_i^B is the solution of eqn(27), and the means of upper bound and lower bound.

4. NUMERICAL EXAMPLE

4.1 Analysis of a Composite Laminated Plate

Fig. 1 shows the geometry of plate. Material property is as follows.

$a = 1.5$ (m)			
$b = 0.375$ (m)			
$t_1 = 1.95$ (cm)	$\theta_1 = 90^\circ$	} Symmetric	(27)
$t_2 = 1.3$ (cm)	$\theta_2 = 90^\circ$		
$t_3 = 3.34$ (cm)	$\theta_3 = 0^\circ$		
$E_1 = 55$ (GPa)	$E_2 = 18.3$ (GPa)		
$G_{12} = G_{13} = 9.1$ (GPa)	$G_{23} = 4.55$ (GPa)		
$\nu_{12} = 0.25$	$\rho = 1993$ (Kg/m ³)		
$\Psi_{11} = 0$			
$\Psi_{22} = \Psi_{23} = \Psi_{13} = \Psi_{12} = 0.5$			

To solve an eigen-problem, Eispack-Subroutine^[10] is used. The FEM model is an 8-nodes element which has five degrees of freedom per node. The model and boundary condition is shown in Fig. 2. When the concentrated load of 5×10^6 N is applied at the grid No. 21 in Fig.2, the deflection at the central point of

FIGURE 1. Geometry and coordinate system of plate and its section of a hybrid composite.

the plate is 21.1mm in this study and 27.8mm in COSMIC/NASTRAN. This seems due to the shear correction factor(5/6) which is adopted, although the thickness of the plate with its ratio ($a/t=11.38$, $b/t=2.845$) is too thick. However, the each natural frequency is 1573Hz, 1553Hz in this study and COSMIC/NASTRAN analysis. The result in this paper is higher than the NASTRAN analysis by 1.3%. The S.D.C. in Ref.[9] is 0.482 for the 0° ply angle and 0.0216 for the 90° ply angle and the calculated value in this study is 0.482 for the 0° ply angle and 0.0230 for the 90° ply angle.

FIGURE 2. Finite element mesh generation and boundary conditions.

Optimization procedures to use FEM is made as Fig. 3, and used for the optimal design of composite laminated plate and hybrid composite laminated plate.

FIGURE 3. Flow chart of the optimization program

4.2 Design of Ply Angle for the Composite Laminated Plate

The each calculated result for multi-object functions for the design of the GFRP material plate ($a/t=150$, $a=1500\text{mm}$), which is initially plied 45° , is that the

deflection of plate is minimum, at 112.5°, that the natural frequency is maximum at 99.37° and that the maximum S.D.C. for the initial ply sequence of [45°, -45°]_s is obtained at the ply angle, ±3.75°. Fig. 4 shows the ply angle change according to the iteration numbers for the S.D.C. In Fig. 4, the ply angle is approaching to 0° as the iteration number increases.

FIGURE 4. Variation of the ply angle with number of iteration for simply supported laminated plate(S.D.C.)

4.3 Design of Ply Thickness for a Composite Laminated Plate

The result for the design example whose chosen design parameter is ply angle is listed in Table 1. In order to compares with reference, the initial value of

TABLE 1. Initial and final design values of thickness variables for simply supported laminated plate(GFRP, a/b=4)

	Layer No.	Ply Angle (deg)	Ply Thickness		Weight(kgf)		Constraint Values		
			Initial (mm)	Final (mm)	Initial	Final	U _{max} (30)	f _{min} (1592)	V _{min} (0.250)
Case 1	1	90	30	13.6	179.37	143.27	22.4	1562	0.250
	2	90	20	20.0					
	3	0	30	30.3					
Case 2	1	99.37	30	12.7	179.37	142.82	22.4	1560	0.253
	2	99.37	20	22.1					
	3	0	30	28.9					
Case 3	1	112.5	30	20.3	179.37	154.03	20.7	1560	0.301
	2	112.5	20	20.0					
	3	0	30	28.4					
[6] Ref.	1	90	30	19.5	179.37	147.75	21.1	1572	0.26
	2	90	20	13.0					
	3	0	30	33.4					

the case 1 is the same as that of the Ref. [6]. The case 2 shows the ply thickness, when the ply angle which obtained as the design result on the maximum frequency is adopted as the previous values. The case 3 shows the ply thickness, when the ply angle which obtained as the design result on the minimum deflection is adopted as design previous values. The convergence criteria is that the weight varies within 1%, that each variation of design constraint is restricted within 2%, and the variation of error sum is restricted within 1% in the each design step. When the result of the case 1 in Table 1 is compared with that of Ref[6], it is shown that the differences of each ply thickness is due to the difference of optimization procedure and convergence criteria.

4.4 Design of Ply Thickness for the Hybrid Laminated Plate

In this paper, the optimization design of the hybrid laminated composite plate which is composed of aluminum alloy and GFRP plied in the sequence of [45°, -45°]_s, is carried out. The material property of aluminum ally used, is assumed as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_1 &= E_2 = 68.9457 \text{ (Gpa)} \\
 G_{12} &= G_{13} = G_{23} = 26.5183 \text{ (Gpa)} \\
 \nu_{12} &= 0.3, \quad \rho = 2675 \text{ (Kg/m}^3\text{)} \\
 \Psi_{11} &= \Psi_{22} = \Psi_{23} = \Psi_{13} = \Psi_{12} = 0.02
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{28}$$

The design result of hybrid laminated composite plate is listed in Table 2.

TABLE 2. Initial and final design for simply supported hybrid laminated plate considered to all constraints

Case No.	Layer No.	Ply Angle (deg)	Ply Thickness		Weight(kgf)		Constraint Values		
			Initial (mm)	Final (mm)	Initial	Final	U _{max} (30)	f _{min} (1592)	Ψ _{min} (0.250)
Case 1	1	A1	30	3.03	202.39	163.53	19.0	1560.0	0.276
	2	45	20	8.53					
	3	-45	30	60.34					
Case 2	1	45	30	31.1	194.72	167.99	15.5	1560.0	0.255
	2	A1	20	10.3					
	3	-45	30	30.0					
Case 3	1	45	30	43.3	202.39	187.06	11.8	1622.0	0.250
	2	-45	20	-					
	3	A1	30	29.9					

When this result is compared with that of Table 1, it is shown that the design weight of the hybrid laminated composite plate is heavier than that of GFRP

composite laminated plate. This is due to that the GFRP material is superior to the isotropic material in the S.D.C. Therefore, in the case that the minimum S.D.C. is smaller than 0.25, the lighter design weight can be obtained. This result can be known from Table 3. Where the S.D.C. is not considered as the design constraint. The convergence criteria used in this designs is the same as that of the above paragraph 4.3

4.5 Design of Ply Thickness for the Hybrid Laminated Plate except S.D.C.

In design of the hybrid laminated composite plate, the S.D.C. of isotropic material is so small that influences the optimization design. Therefore, the only minimum deflection and maximum natural frequency is chosen as the design constraint. The design result listed in Table 3 can be obtained. In Table 3, the design weight of the Case 1 decreases from 163.53 Kgf of Table 2 to 137.39 Kgf and that of the Case 2 decreases from 167.99 Kgf to 115.88 Kgf and that of the Case 3 decreases from 187.06 Kgf to 160.82 Kgf.

TABLE 3 Initial and final design for simply supported hybrid laminated plate without S.D.C. constraint.

Case No.	Layer No.	Ply Angle (deg)	Ply Thickness		Weight(kgf)		Constraint Values		
			Initial (mm)	Final (mm)	Initial	Final	U_{max} (30)	f_{min} (1592)	Ψ_{min} (0.0)
Case 1	1	A1	30	8.7	202.39	137.39	19.4	1560.0	0.169
	2	45	20	20.0					
	3	-45	30	29.6					
Case 2	1	45	30	0.0	194.72	115.88	21.8	1560.0	0.067
	2	A1	20	16.9					
	3	-45	30	29.0					
Case 3	1	45	30	12.4	202.39	160.82	14.6	1560.0	0.168
	2	-45	20	20.0					
	3	A1	30	29.3					

So, it can be known that the newly defined design constraint is useful in the viewpoint of minimum weight.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The optimization design of the hybrid laminated composite plate composed of aluminum alloy and composite material, GFRP is performed, and following conclusions are obtained.

1. By using FEM, the optimization design can be applied to any boundary condition or any plied sequence of various materials.

2. By using the recursive linear programming method, it is tried to solve the nonlinear optimization problem. The iteration number can be reduced by introducing the design scaling factor for the design variables.

3. The static and dynamic characteristics is simultaneously considered as the design constraint. Also, the ply angle or ply thickness is adopted as the design variable.

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